

EFFECTS OF PROCESSING CONDITION ON MORPHOLOGY AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF PP/PP COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACTS

Composites consisting of the same thermoplastic material for the matrix phase and reinforcement, the so-called ‘polymer unity composites’, are gaining increasing attention. These composites, typically those made from polypropylene (PP) and/or polyethylene (PE), possess distinct properties with potential unique applications. Unlike the conventional composites containing glass or carbon fibres embedded in polymer matrices, they can be easily recycled as they do not require the tedious process to separate the reinforcement fibres from the matrix before individual recycling. These composites can be called the ‘green composites’ as they are more environment-friendly than other composite materials in terms of ease of recycling.

In the present study, the effects of processing conditions are investigated on the morphology and important mechanical properties of all PP composites consisting of homo-PP fibers and propylene-ethylene random copolymer matrix. Highly oriented PP fibres are spun, and composite laminates of different cooling rates and thermal treatments are prepared using the filming stacking and compression molding techniques. The fibre-matrix interfacial bond strengths and the composite bulk mechanical properties are measured, which are in turn correlated to crystallinity and crystalline morphology affected by the processing condition. The single filament fragmentation test shows that the slow cooled samples have higher interfacial shear strengths (IFSS) than the fast cooled ones. The tensile modulus and strength generally increase with decreasing cooling rate and due to isothermal treatment. This observation can be attributed to the change in the crystallinity induced by different thermal processes. A higher crystallinity in the slow cooled samples gives rise to high tensile properties and a brittle fracture mechanism, and vice versa. There are functionally similar variations in IFSS and tensile properties with respect to cooling rate. The Charpy impact test results indicate that the impact fracture performance of the composites is highly dependent on the testing temperature. There were only marginal differences in impact fracture toughness between the samples processed at different cooling rates when tested at room temperature. The sensitivity of cooling rate on impact fracture energy became significant when tested at sub-zero temperatures. The impact fracture toughness are generally higher for the samples with slower cooling rates than the fast cooled samples.

Key terms: PP/PP composites, recycling; crystallinity, interfacial adhesion; mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

‘Polymer Unity Composite’ [1] - typically ‘All PP Composite’ [2] - is defined as the composite consisting of the identical polymer for the reinforcement and the matrix. This type of composite can be fabricated by utilizing the difference in the melting point between the high drawing polymer fibres and matrix materials. Polyethylene-polyethylene (PE-PE) composites with ultrahigh modulus

polyethylene (UHMPE) as the reinforcement have also been developed for various unique applications [3,4]. Apart from the ease with recycling, another advantage of ‘all PP’ or ‘all PE’ composites is a high potential of forming a relatively strong interface between the fiber and matrix without having to apply a fibre surface treatment. For conventional composites, fibre surface treatments are always necessary for a number of reasons, e.g. to enhance the chemical and physical compatibility of the fibre with the matrix material and thus to produce high strength and high stiffness composites.

The interfacial adhesion and bulk mechanical properties of semicrystalline thermoplastic composites can be tailored by optimizing the composite processing conditions, especially the cooling rate during consolidation. Previous studies on ‘all PE’ composites showed that the applications of isothermal treatment and annealing process have a positive effect on the growth of transcrystalline interphase that develops between the fiber and the matrix [3,4]. However, the effect of transcrystalline interphase on the bulk mechanical properties is rather inconclusive. Very few studies have been reported for ‘all PP’ composites thus far. A major objective of this work is, therefore, to develop techniques to fabricate ‘all PP’ composites possessing optimized mechanical properties and damage resistance. The effects of processing conditions are studied on crystalline morphology, crystallinity and the fibre-matrix interfacial bond strength, which are in turn correlated to the bulk mechanical properties and fracture behaviour of the composite.

Figure 1 Schematic diagrams of fibre drawing process

FABRICATION OF ALL PP COMPOSITES

All PP composites were manufactured with drawn homo-polypropylene (HX100G: Sumitomo Chemical Co. Ltd.) as the reinforcement and about 50 μ m thick propylene-ethylene random copolymer film (RS160XGP: Sumitomo Chemical Co. Ltd.) as the bulk matrix. The PP fibre was manufactured by melt-spinning the homo-PP polymer using 10-hole spinneret of 0.6mm in diameter at 200°C with an output/throughput rate of 15g/min. The PP fibre was then made into 10-filament bundles by extruding the melt-spun fibre on a spinneret high speed winding and drawing machine at a take up rate of 1km/min, as ‘neat fibre’. The neat fibre then underwent a heat treatment and a drawing processes on a drawing machine (HW-500: Ohba Kikai) to produce ‘drawn fibre’ for composite fabrication, as shown in Figure 1. The average diameter of drawn fibres was 18.3 μ m, as measured using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Tensile test of the drawn PP fibre was conducted to verify the improvements of tensile properties due to the heat treatment and drawing processes, and the results are presented in Table 1. It is seen that the heat treatment enhanced the tensile modulus and strength by 10% and 39% respectively. After the drawing process, its tensile strength was further improved by 49%, although there was a marginal reduction in tensile modulus. The melting points of the PP film and drawn PP fibre are 139°C and 170°C, respectively, as measured using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC).

Film stacking and compression molding methods were employed to produce all PP preregs and laminate composite plates. Preregs of 250mm square and 10% fibre vol. fraction were fabricated from alternating layers of PP film and continuous unidirectional PP fibre at 150°C and a pressure of

1.9MPa. Laminate composite plates were moulded using the unidirectional preregs on a programmable hot press machine (PHI DT5000). The molding temperature of 165°C was chosen to allow complete melting of the matrix material with partial surface melting of PP fibre so that a strong bond between the PP fibre and matrix could be formed. As the mould pressure increased gradually along with the temperature increase, the mould was held at 1.9MPa after the temperature reached 165°C as well as during cooling to ambient. The thickness of the composite plate was controlled by inserting suitable spacing blocks between the mould plates. Several different cooling rates were used to produce laminates having different properties, as shown in Table 2.

Table 1 Tensile properties of ‘neat’, ‘heat-treated’ and ‘drawn’ PP fibre

Process	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)
Neat Fibre	291.1	3.48
Heat-treated Fibre	319.9	4.82
Drawn Fibre	477.9	3.2

Table 2 Different thermal conditions used in composite fabrication

Condition	Holding time at 165°C (min)	Isothermal temperature (°C)	Isothermal holding time (min)	Cooling rate (°C/min)
Fast-cooled-I	30	N/A	N/A	50
Intermediate-cooled-I	30	N/A	N/A	8
Intermediate-cooled-II	1	N/A	N/A	11
ISO-I	30	89	120	8
ISO-II	1	89	30	11
ISO-III	1	89	120	11
ISO-IV	1	105	120	11
Slow-cooled-I	30	N/A	N/A	1
Slow-cooled-II	1	N/A	N/A	3

MORPHOLOGY AND CRYSTALLINITY OF ALL PP COMPOSITES

For semicrystalline polymer composites, it is well known that the crystallinity, the melting point and the cooling rate are closely interrelated. The crystalline morphology of the composites is in turn significantly affected by cooling rate and thermal conditions used in the manufacturing processes. Therefore, both the microstructural morphology and the degree of crystallinity of all PP composites is a direct reflection of the effect of the thermal conditions. Optical microscopes equipped with polarized light filters were used to characterize the crystalline morphology of composite specimens of approximately 10µm in thickness. The crystallinities of all PP composites were measured using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, SETAPRAM 92). Specimens of about 30mg were analyzed in nitrogen at a heating rate of 10°C/min. The degree of crystallinity (X_c) was calculated:

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m - \Delta H_c}{\Delta H_f (1 - \alpha)} \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_m and ΔH_c are the enthalpy of fusion at the melting point as measured by the area under the endothermic peak, and the enthalpy of crystallization as measured by the area under the exothermic crystallization peak, respectively. ΔH_f is the enthalpy of fusion of fully crystalline PP, which is taken as 165J/g, and α is the mass fraction of PP fibre in the composite.

The crystalline morphologies of PP matrices are shown in Figure 2. The size of spherulites generally increased as the cooling rate decreased. For the isothermally (ISO) conditioned specimen, the matrix crystalline morphology was comparable to that of the intermediate-cooled sample. This could be due to the similar cooling rate used in these two conditions, indicating a more pronounced effect of cooling rate on constructing crystalline morphology than isothermal condition. Previous studies showed that the cooling rate has a strong influence on the spherulite size of semicrystalline polymers, and the spherulite size increased with increasing molecular perfection and melting temperature [5,6]. The dependence of crystallite size on cooling rate could be explained from the viewpoint of molecular movement [7]. The mobility of polymer chains is discouraged at high cooling rates, thus limiting the diffusion ability of polymer chains to the growing crystal front.

Figure 2 Optical micrographs of spherulite morphology of (a) fast-cooled, (b) intermediate-cooled, (c) slow-cooled and (d) ISO specimens (250x magnification)

The examination of the fibre-matrix interphase region suggested that transcrystalline was not formed in the fast- and intermediate-cooled specimens. A better-defined and relatively thick transcrystalline interphase was observed in the ISO specimen, which was oriented perpendicularly to the fiber surface and has a slightly different morphology from that of the matrix (Figure 3(a)). Previous studies on carbon or Kevlar fibre-PP composites [8] showed that an isothermal treatment could help promote a thick transcrystalline layer on the fibre surface. The nucleation and growth of spherulites from the surface of carbon fibre is often related to the graphitic nature of the fibre surface instead of the fibre surface chemistry [9]. It should be noted that the crystalline structure of PP appeared to be different from composites reinforced with carbon or glass fibres, due to the difference in moulding temperature used to fabricate the composite. The processing temperature used to melt the PP matrix in the conventional fibre composites is often 200°C or higher, allowing the residual thermal effect present in the polymer to be completely erased after moulding. Thus, well defined and large spherulitic crystal structure could be formed (Figure 3(c)). However, the moulding temperature used for all PP composites in the present work had to be much lower than 200°C due to the limitation of low m.t. of PP fibres used (170°C). When moulded at a higher temperature of 200°C, the PP fibres completely melted and could not function as reinforcement (Figure 3(b)).

Figure 3 Optical micrographs of the morphology of slow-cooled specimens that are moulded at (a) 165°C and (b), (c) 200°C. (250x magnification)

The crystallinity of neat PP matrix and all PP composites manufactured in different thermal conditions were measured using the DSC, and the results are presented in Table 3. The melting point of both the neat PP matrix and PP fibre marginally increased as the cooling rate decreased, as affected by several factors, such as crystal size, fold surface energy and plate. The degree of crystallinity in general increased with decreasing cooling rate, which agrees with previous studies on semicrystalline polymer composites [7]. It is also noted that both X_c and m.p. for different all PP composites were slightly lower than those for the equivalent neat PP matrix. Similar phenomena were also observed in carbon fibre semicrystalline thermoplastic composites [7], which were attributed to the suppression of growth of spherulites in the presence of densely packed fibres within the matrix, thus offsetting the ameliorating effect of the fibre surface as preferred crystallite nucleation sites.

Table 3. Melting points and degree of crystallinity for neat PP matrix and all PP composite.

Thermal condition		T_{m-m} (°C)	T_{m-f} (°C)	X_c
All PP composite	Fast-cooled-I	138.70	174.92	27.3
	Intermediate-cooled-I	138.46	174.62	29.9
	ISO-I	139.04	174.88	29.4
	Slow-cooled-I	141.10	177.18	31.1
Neat PP matrix	Fast-cooled-I	138.45	N/A	31.6
	Intermediate-cooled-I	140.08	N/A	30.8
	ISO-I	139.88	N/A	29.8
	Slow-cooled-I	140.49	N/A	34.1

- T_{m-m}, T_{m-f} : Melting points of PP matrix and PP fibre, respectively.

FIBRE-MATRIX INTERFACIAL ADHESION IN ALL PP COMPOSITES

The fragmentation test composite plates were prepared by embedding PP fibres between two PP matrix films, which were molded in a hot press at different thermal conditions. The single fibre fragmentation specimens were cut into a dog-bone shape having a gage length of 5mm from the moulded plates. The fragmentation test was carried out on a Minimat testing machine at a cross head speed of 10mm/min. While increasing the tensile load, fibre fragmentation was monitored using a polarised light microscope attached with a computer controlled video recorder. The load-displacement curves were obtained from the built-in data logging system of the tester. The fibre fragment lengths were measured after the test using a measuring microscope (Topcon TMM-13OZ). The critical transfer length l_c was calculated from the measured mean fibre fragment length \bar{l} :

$$l_c = \frac{4\bar{l}}{3} \quad (2)$$

The interfacial shear strength τ_c was evaluated from the simple Kelly-Tyson relationship, where σ_f is the strength of fiber:

$$\tau_c = \frac{d\sigma_f}{l_c} \quad (3)$$

Figure 4. The cumulative distributions of fibre fragment lengths

The cumulative distributions of fibre fragment lengths obtained from five specimens of the identical processing conditions are plotted Figure 4. The statistical variations of fibre fragment length for different processing conditions were very similar. However, there was a slight shift of the curves for the slow-cooled and ISO specimens to the left relative to that of the fast-cooled specimens, indicating improved stress transfer efficiency in these specimens. The fibre-matrix interfacial shear strengths (IFSS) increased as the cooling rate decreased, as shown in Figure 5.

The fragmentation processes of fast-cooled and slow-cooled specimens were studied, identifying different fibre fracture and debonding behaviours between the two conditions. For fast-cooled specimens, the fibre fragment ends were relatively irregular in shape, indicating ductile fibre fracture. The debonded interface appeared during the entire tensile loading as a black cylindrical void between the fibre and matrix, a reflection of ductile PP matrix and weak interfacial adhesion. For slow-cooled specimens, the voids between the fragment fibre ends appeared as an elongated diamond

shape only in the final stage of loading, indicating relatively stiff matrix and strong interfacial adhesion [7].

Figure 5. Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) for different processing conditions

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ALL PP COMPOSITES

The dog-bone shaped tensile specimens with different processing conditions were prepared using a metallic mould according to the specification, ASTM D638. Tensile tests were carried out on a universal testing machine at room temperature at a constant displacement rate of 1mm/min. The tensile strength and tensile modulus were determined from the load-displacement curves recorded from the data acquisition system. The tensile tests were performed at four different testing temperatures, -40°C , 0°C , 25°C and 50°C in an environmental chamber. The true displacements were obtained using a video extensometer for tests at 25°C and 50°C , and using a strain extensometer for tests at lower temperatures.

The Charpy impact test specimens were fabricated using all PP unidirectional fibre composites according to the specification ASTM D265. Notches were made at the mid-span of rectangular specimens using a notching machine (CEAST Razor Notching Machine) and sharpened using a razor blade. The Charpy impact tests were conducted using a pendulum-type impact test machine (CEAST) at two different testing temperatures, at 25°C and -70°C . The energy absorbed by the specimens was calculated from the difference in potential energy of the impact hammer before and after impact. For the impact test at -70°C , the specimens were placed into a bag of dry ice for 30 min., where a uniform equilibrium temperature was maintained at -70°C in the specimen.

Figure 6. Tensile strength and modulus versus stacking sequence of all PP composites

The tensile strength and modulus data are presented for all PP composites with different stacking sequences. As expected, both the strength and modulus were highest in the longitudinal direction, $[0]_4$, and lowest in the transverse direction, $[90]_4$. For composites with cross plies, $[0/90]_s$, $[90/0]_s$ and $[0/90]_2$, the tensile strength and modulus were very similar each other, due to the low volume fraction of fibre and the same number of 0° layers.

The effects of processing condition and testing temperature on tensile strength and modulus for all PP composites are shown in Figure 7. The tensile strength increased with decreasing cooling rate and isothermal treatment at all testing temperatures, as a result of higher crystallinity for the slow-cooled specimens. The dependence of tensile strength on cooling rate was more pronounced at a sub-zero temperature than an elevated temperature, indicating that the matrix crystallinity became more influential on composite tensile strength with decreasing testing temperature. However, the tensile modulus increased with decreasing cooling rate only at high temperatures, 25°C and 50°C . At low temperatures, 0°C and -40°C , the variation of tensile modulus with processing condition was rather inconclusive. Previous studies [10] showed that the longitudinal tensile properties of semicrystalline PEEK matrix composites were less sensitive to cooling rate when tested at room temperature.

The tensile failure mechanisms were generally similar between the composites with different processing conditions. However, the testing temperature had a significant influence on failure mechanism as with the tensile properties, as shown in Figure 8. At a sub-zero temperature, -40°C , the tensile samples failed by transverse rupture with cracks propagating right through the sample cross section in a brittle manner, whereas at high temperatures, 25°C and 50°C , longitudinal splitting took place along the fibre length before rupture in the transverse direction. A transition of failure mechanism occurred at 0°C where both the longitudinal splitting and transverse rupture took place almost simultaneously. These distinct failure mechanisms appear to reflect the sensitivity of fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion and matrix ductility on testing temperature.

Figure 7. Variations of (a) tensile strength and (b) tensile modulus of unidirectional all PP composites of different processing conditions tested at different temperatures.

Figure 8. Fractured all PP composite specimens made with isothermal treatment tested at different temperatures.

The impact fracture toughness of unidirectional all PP composites is presented in Figure 9 for different processing conditions. It is seen that the fracture toughness increased with decreasing cooling rate or due to isothermal treatment, regardless of testing temperature. The improved fracture toughness is correlated to the higher crystallinity at a slow cooling rate. Unlike the tensile properties discussed above, the fracture toughness was much higher when tested at room temperature than at a sub-zero temperature, -70°C . The specimens tested at room temperature showed significant plastic deformation, and were not completely broken. The degree of plastic deformation increased with decreasing cooling rate. In contrast, the specimens tested at -70°C were completely broken with planar fracture surfaces without showing any plastic deformation. It is seen that the fracture toughness of all PP composites containing a low fibre volume fraction is controlled mainly by the matrix ductility that is in turn sensitive to the crystallinity and testing temperature.

Figure 9 Fracture toughness of unidirectional all PP composites with different processing conditions impacted at room temperature and -70°C

CONCLUDING REMARKS

All PP composites were successfully produced based on the film stacking and compression moulding techniques. The effect of cooling rate on the morphology, fiber-matrix interfacial properties, tensile properties and impact fracture toughness of all PP composites were investigated. It is found that there were strong correlations between the thermal processing condition and the degree, morphology and structure of crystallinity and fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion, which in turn controlled the bulk composite mechanical properties. The spherulite size and crystallinity of the bulk PP matrix increased with decreasing cooling rate. The interfacial bond strength was higher in composites produced at a slow cooling rate and isothermal treatment. Both the tensile properties and impact fracture toughness could be improved by introducing a transcrystalline interphase when a slow cooling process and an isothermal treatment are employed. There was a transition of failure mechanism due to testing temperature in uniaxial tension of the unidirectional composites: at a high temperature, longitudinal splitting is dominant with much lower tensile modulus and strength, whereas at a sub-zero temperature transverse fracture occurred in a brittle manner with much higher tensile properties. These distinct failure mechanisms appear to reflect the sensitivity of fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion and matrix ductility on testing temperature.

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